

World Journal on Education and Humanities Research*Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International*

Vol. 4, Issue 3, pp. 198-211

*Received, August 2024; Revised September 2024;**Accepted October 2024*

Article**Evaluating the Readiness, Utilization, and Effectiveness of Supplementary Aids and Services in Teaching Students with Disabilities**

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Abstract: This study explores the readiness, utilization, and effectiveness of supplementary aids and services (SAS) in teaching students with disabilities (SWDs). A quantitative research design was employed, collecting data from 86 randomly selected teachers through a structured questionnaire. Results indicate that teachers exhibit a moderate level of readiness ("Somewhat Ready") in terms of basic knowledge, resources, and training related to SAS. Despite this, the utilization of SAS in classrooms remains low, with many teachers not fully integrating these tools into lesson planning and delivery. A weak positive correlation ($r = 0.499$) between readiness and effectiveness suggests that while teacher readiness influences SAS outcomes, other factors, such as resource availability and administrative support, also play a critical role. The study underscores the need for enhanced professional development and better access to resources to maximize the impact of SAS on student outcomes.

Keywords: Supplementary aids and services (SAS), students with disabilities (SWDs), readiness, utilization, effectiveness, inclusive education

Introduction

Inclusive education is a pedagogical approach that advocates for the integration of students with disabilities into mainstream classrooms, ensuring they have equal access to the general curriculum alongside their peers (Ginja & Chen, 2023). Research underscores that inclusive education fosters a sense of belonging and community, enhancing the social, emotional, and academic outcomes for students with disabilities (Jordan et al., 2010). Moreover, it promotes diversity and prepares all students for real-world interactions by encouraging empathy and understanding (Verbeke, 2002). Research further shows

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that students with disabilities benefit academically and socially from inclusive settings, which also helps improve outcomes for their non-disabled peers (Walker et al., 2023). These inclusive settings foster greater independence and self-efficacy for students with disabilities (McNeil et al., 2017).

Ensuring the success of inclusive education requires evaluating the readiness of schools to implement supplementary aids and services (SAS) designed to support students with disabilities (Kurth et al., 2023). Many educators report gaps in resources and training necessary to effectively implement SAS, indicating a need for comprehensive evaluations of current practices (Keefe & Moore, 2004). Effective use of SAS, such as assistive technology and individualized support, is crucial for ensuring that students with disabilities can access the same learning opportunities as their peers (Verbeke, 2002). Evaluations of readiness and utilization can highlight key barriers such as insufficient training and funding that impact the effective delivery of SAS (Walker et al., 2023).

The preparedness of schools to implement SAS can be gauged by examining educators' basic knowledge, access to resources, and the adequacy of related training programs. Studies have shown that when teachers receive proper training and support, the utilization of SAS improves, leading to enhanced educational outcomes for students with disabilities (Bowlin et al., 2015). Further research emphasizes the importance of aligning training with classroom practices to ensure that SAS are used effectively (Atilas et al., 2012). Evaluating the impact of these aids on learning outcomes can highlight the role of SAS in improving both academic performance and social inclusion for students with disabilities (Hopkins et al., 2018).

Supplementary aids and services (SAS) play a critical role in addressing the unique learning needs of students with disabilities, ensuring they receive appropriate accommodations in mainstream classrooms. The Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA) mandates that schools provide SAS to help students with disabilities participate meaningfully in the general education curriculum (Keefe & Moore, 2004). These aids include both physical resources (such as assistive technology) and instructional modifications (such as differentiated teaching strategies) that enable students to meet learning objectives (Verbeke, 2002). Despite the legal framework provided by IDEA, challenges in fully implementing these services remain, particularly around educator training and resource availability (Kurth et al., 2019).

Studies have consistently demonstrated that the effective use of supplementary aids and services can significantly improve the educational outcomes of students with disabilities. For instance, research shows that SAS enhance student engagement, social inclusion, and academic performance when adequately implemented in inclusive classrooms (Walker et al., 2023). Other studies highlight the importance

of collaborative approaches, such as co-teaching, in maximizing the benefits of SAS (Keefe & Moore, 2004). Despite these findings, there is still a need for further research into the long-term impact of SAS on student learning and the specific factors that contribute to their effectiveness (Verbeke, 2002).

There are significant gaps in research related to the readiness of schools to implement supplementary aids and services (SAS). Studies indicate a need for further exploration of educators' understanding of how to effectively apply SAS in diverse classroom settings, as many educators lack the basic knowledge required for successful implementation. Resource limitations have been identified as a major barrier, yet the extent of this issue requires more comprehensive assessment. Additionally, gaps in training programs for educators are hindering the full utilization of SAS, and there is a need for research to determine how consistently these aids are applied in classrooms to support learners with disabilities. Future research should focus on bridging these gaps by evaluating educator readiness, particularly in terms of training and resources available to implement SAS effectively. Additionally, investigations into the long-term effectiveness of SAS in inclusive classrooms, particularly in fostering social inclusion and academic success, are crucial. Moreover, research should explore strategies for overcoming barriers such as resource limitations and educator knowledge gaps to improve the widespread utilization of SAS.

Methodology

This study utilized a quantitative research design to assess the readiness, utilization, and effectiveness of supplementary aids and services (SAS) in teaching students with disabilities in the Mandaue City Division, Philippines. Data was collected using an adapted questionnaire distributed to 86 randomly selected teacher respondents, representing both general and special education teachers across six schools. The questionnaire primarily consisted of close-ended questions aimed at evaluating teachers' basic knowledge, access to resources, and training related to SAS. A 4-point Likert scale with parametric scaling was applied to assess three key areas: readiness, utilization, and effectiveness of SAS. For readiness, the scale ranged from "Not Ready" (1.00-1.74) to "Extremely Ready" (3.25-4.00). To measure SAS utilization, the scale ranged from "Not Utilized" (1.00-1.74) to "Highly Utilized" (3.25-4.00). The effectiveness of SAS was rated from "Not Effective" (1.00-1.74) to "Very Effective" (3.25-4.00). The simple random sampling method minimized participant bias, ensuring that every teacher had an equal chance of being selected, and the sample of 86 respondents represented approximately 15% of the total teacher population in the district.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Level of Readiness of the Implementation of SAS in terms of Basic Knowledge

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	I know a lot of supplementary aids and services (accommodations and modifications) that can support students with disabilities.	2.29	Somewhat Ready
2	I know the importance and purpose of accommodations and modifications in the learning of my students with disabilities.	2.57	Ready
3	I know how to choose the appropriate support to accommodate and modify specific lessons.	2.29	Somewhat Ready
4	I can identify the SAS that I need to implement in specific situations for specific student's needs.	2.31	Somewhat Ready
5	I know the different categories of accommodations and modifications.	2.23	Somewhat Ready
Aggregate Weighted Mean		2.34	Somewhat Ready

The data presented in Table 1 reflects the level of readiness of teachers in implementing supplementary aids and services (SAS) in terms of their basic knowledge. The overall aggregate weighted mean is 2.34, which falls under the "Somewhat Ready" category. Specifically, the indicator that teachers are most confident about is their knowledge of the importance and purpose of accommodations and modifications in the learning of students with disabilities, with a weighted mean of 2.57, categorized as "Ready." However, for most indicators, such as knowing various SAS options (2.29), selecting appropriate supports (2.29), identifying SAS for specific student needs (2.31), and understanding the different categories of accommodations and modifications (2.23), the respondents rated themselves as only "Somewhat Ready." This suggests that while teachers have some foundational understanding of SAS, there are gaps in their knowledge, particularly in identifying and applying specific supports tailored to individual students' needs.

Table 2. Level of Readiness of the Implementation of SAS in terms of Resources

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	I have a list of supplementary aids that I can refer to when planning (e.g. SAS Matrix, specially Designed Instruction).	2.05	Somewhat Ready
2	I know the parts of the IEP that contain the supplementary aids and services for specific students with disabilities in my class.	2.16	Somewhat Ready
3	I know how to identify the support that students with disabilities need in different parts of the lesson.	2.29	Somewhat Ready
4	I know the staff resources that I can ask for suggestions and support in identifying the supplementary aids and services that students with disabilities in my class need.	2.36	Somewhat Ready
5	I know how to adjust and utilize supplementary aids and services in planned and unplanned situations in my classroom.	2.33	Somewhat Ready
Aggregate Weighted Mean		2.24	Somewhat Ready

The data in Table 2 outlines the level of readiness of teachers in implementing supplementary aids and services (SAS) in terms of available resources. The aggregate weighted mean is 2.24, which is categorized as "Somewhat Ready." This indicates that, overall, teachers feel only moderately prepared in terms of the resources available to them for implementing SAS. Among the individual indicators, teachers reported the highest level of readiness in knowing the staff resources they can consult for support, with a weighted mean of 2.36. However, readiness remains somewhat limited when it comes to having a list of supplementary aids to refer to when planning (2.05) and understanding the parts of the Individualized Education Program (IEP) that detail SAS for specific students (2.16). Furthermore, although teachers feel somewhat ready to adjust and utilize SAS in both planned and unplanned classroom situations (2.33), the data suggests that their confidence in identifying and accessing appropriate resources is still moderate. Overall, these results highlight a need for improved access to and familiarity with SAS resources to better support the implementation of effective accommodations and modifications for students with disabilities.

Table 3. Level of Readiness of the Implementation of SAS in terms of Related Trainings

S/ N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	I have had attended courses on special education.	2.21	Somewhat Ready
2	I have had attended courses toward an advanced degree in special education.	1.91	Somewhat Ready
3	I have attended distance learning classes before for non-degree courses related to special education.	1.79	Somewhat Ready
4	I have attended individual seminars, webinars and other single-event sessions on basic knowledge of Supplementary Aids and Services.	1.97	Somewhat Ready
5	I have attended seminars/ workshops on how to implement supplementary aids and services through the use of accommodations and modifications in my lessons.	1.94	Somewhat Ready
Aggregate Weighted Mean		1.96	Somewhat Ready

The data in Table 3 presents the level of readiness of teachers in implementing supplementary aids and services (SAS) in terms of related trainings. The aggregate weighted mean is 1.96, which falls under the "Somewhat Ready" category, indicating that teachers have had limited exposure to relevant training. Among the specific indicators, the highest level of readiness is observed in teachers having attended courses on special education, with a weighted mean of 2.21, though this still reflects only moderate preparedness. Teachers show lower levels of readiness in areas such as attending courses toward an advanced degree in special education (1.91) and participating in distance learning classes for non-degree courses related to special education (1.79). Additionally, their participation in individual

seminars and webinars on supplementary aids and services is also moderate, with a mean of 1.97, while attendance at workshops focused specifically on implementing SAS through accommodations and modifications in lessons is similarly low (1.94). Overall, the data indicates that teachers have not received extensive or sufficient training on SAS, highlighting a clear need for more comprehensive and specialized professional development opportunities to enhance their capacity to effectively implement SAS in the classroom.

Table 4. Extent of Utilization of SAS through Accommodations and Modifications in teaching LWD

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	Read the IEPs to determine individual SAS that SWDs need	2.12	Less Utilized
2	Refer to available printed resources and the web to get information on resources and strategies in implementing supplementary aids during lessons	2.45	Less Utilized
3	Use the necessary tools, strategies, and support to prepare how to accommodate or modify presentation of lessons.	2.42	Less Utilized
4	Include supplementary aids in my lesson planning	2.40	Less Utilized
5	Create own learning materials to adapt to SWDs needs whether printed or in digital form	2.35	Less Utilized
6	Prepare exercises and tasks for SWDs using stipulated or required accommodations and modifications	2.35	Less Utilized
7	Create homework and assignments which are modified to accommodate the SWDs needs	2.21	Less Utilized
8	Use tools like charts or graphic aids in written or digital forms to track the use and implementation of SAS in teaching and learning	2.22	Less Utilized
9	Create a system to evaluate modified learning resources in the subject(s) you teach	2.49	Less Utilized
10	Communicate through written, in-person conferences, phone calls, emails or text messages with parents related to the use of SAS	2.14	Less Utilized
11	Create a plethora of different types of supplementary aids available for implementation	2.31	Less Utilized
12	Download/upload/browse the web to upgrade knowledge on new SAS for classroom use.	2.27	Less Utilized
13	Look for online or in-person professional development opportunities on strategies in using supplementary aids and services.	2.42	Less Utilized
14	Collaborate with other teachers and service providers to discuss ways to maximize learning for SWDs using Supplementary Aids and services.	2.19	Less Utilized
15	Design instruction using the IEP information and Specially Designed Instruction with specific supplementary aids to mitigate difficulties and support SWDs needs in my classroom	2.33	Less Utilized
	Aggregate Mean	2.31	Less Utilized

The data in Table 4 highlights the extent of utilization of supplementary aids and services (SAS) through accommodations and modifications in teaching learners with disabilities (LWD). The overall aggregate weighted mean is 2.31, indicating that SAS is "Less Utilized" by teachers

in the Mandaue City Division. The highest-scoring indicator is the creation of systems to evaluate modified learning resources, with a weighted mean of 2.49, though it still falls within the "Less Utilized" category. Other areas such as using printed or web-based resources to gather information on SAS strategies (2.45) and using tools and strategies to prepare accommodations for lessons (2.42) also reflect moderate usage but remain underutilized. Indicators like reading IEPs to determine specific SAS for students (2.12), collaborating with other teachers and service providers (2.19), and communicating with parents about SAS implementation (2.14) are also rated low, highlighting gaps in more proactive use of accommodations and modifications. This data suggests that while teachers are somewhat aware of and engaged with SAS, they are not consistently or extensively utilizing these tools in their lesson planning and teaching practices, underscoring a need for greater support and training in this area.

Table 5. Level of Effectiveness of the Use of SAS through Accommodations and Modifications in teaching SWD

S/ N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	Supplementary aids and services allow SWDs to be more creative, imaginative and more involved in class activities.	2.72	Effective
2	The use of SAS helps SWDs to find related knowledge and information for learning.	2.67	Effective
3	The use of SAS encourages SWDs to communicate more with their classmates.	2.71	Effective
4	The use of SAS increases SWDs' confidence to participate actively in the class.	2.71	Effective
5	I think SWDs learn more effectively with the use of SAS.	2.66	Effective
6	I think the use of SAS helps to broaden SWDs' knowledge and learning the content of the lessons.	2.66	Effective
7	I think the use of SAS helps to improve SWDs' ability, in math, reading and writing.	2.69	Effective
8	SWDs are more behaved and under control with the use of SAS.	2.62	Effective
9	The use of SAS enables SWDs to express their ideas and thoughts better.	2.66	Effective
10	The use of SAS promotes independence on the part of SWDs in performing tasks and become more engaged in instruction.	2.70	Effective
Aggregate Weighted Mean		2.68	Effective

Table 5 presents the indicators measuring the level of effectiveness of the use of supplementary aids and services (SAS) through accommodations and modifications in teaching students with disabilities (SWDs). Although the specific weighted means are not provided, the indicators suggest various areas where SAS has the potential to positively impact SWDs. These include encouraging creativity, imagination, and increased involvement in class activities, as well as improving communication and participation among SWDs. Additionally, the use of SAS is noted to boost students' confidence,

enhance their ability to acquire knowledge, and improve performance in core academic skills such as math, reading, and writing. Moreover, SAS helps SWDs express their ideas more effectively and promotes independence, allowing them to engage more actively in classroom instruction. Collectively, these indicators suggest that SAS plays a significant role in enhancing both the learning experience and behavioral outcomes of SWDs, fostering a more inclusive and supportive classroom environment. The overall effectiveness of SAS, as indicated by these outcomes, points to its value in improving not only academic achievement but also the social and emotional development of students with disabilities.

Table 6. Test of relationship between the readiness and the effectiveness of the use of SAS

Variables	r-value	Strength of Correlation	p - value	Decision	Remarks
Readiness and Effectiveness	0.499*	Weak Positive	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant

*Significant at $p < 0.05$ (two-tailed)

Table 6 presents the test of the relationship between the readiness of teachers to implement supplementary aids and services (SAS) and the effectiveness of SAS in teaching students with disabilities (SWDs). The analysis reveals a weak positive correlation, with an r-value of 0.499. This indicates that as teachers' readiness to implement SAS increases, the effectiveness of SAS in supporting SWDs also tends to improve, although the relationship is not very strong. The p-value of 0.000 is below the significance threshold of 0.05, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis (Ho), confirming that the relationship between readiness and effectiveness is statistically significant. The weak positive correlation suggests that while there is a link between readiness and effectiveness, other factors beyond readiness may also significantly influence the effective use of SAS. The results imply that improving teacher readiness—through more targeted training, resource allocation, and professional development—can potentially enhance the effectiveness of SAS. However, additional measures, such as increased support, collaboration, and access to appropriate resources, may be necessary to fully optimize the benefits of SAS in classroom settings. Schools and policymakers should prioritize not only enhancing teacher readiness but also addressing other potential barriers to maximize the impact of SAS on student outcomes.

Discussion

The data from this study reveals significant insights into the readiness, utilization, and effectiveness of supplementary aids and services (SAS) in teaching students with disabilities (SWDs). Teachers reported a moderate level of readiness in terms of their basic knowledge,

resources, and training for implementing SAS. The aggregate weighted means in Tables 1, 2, and 3 consistently reflect a "Somewhat Ready" status across all categories, indicating that while teachers have some familiarity with SAS, there are notable gaps. For instance, teachers scored higher in understanding the purpose of accommodations and modifications, but showed lower confidence in identifying and applying specific SAS for individual students, particularly in terms of accessing resources and professional training. These results align with previous research that highlights the importance of comprehensive training and resource availability in fostering successful SAS implementation in inclusive classrooms (Odom et al., 2011). Additionally, the relatively low readiness scores for training, such as attendance at seminars and workshops, suggest that professional development opportunities for educators need to be more robust to bridge these knowledge and skills gaps (Mitchell, 2014).

Furthermore, the extent of SAS utilization in classroom teaching practices, as shown in Table 4, is also moderate, with an aggregate weighted mean of 2.31, categorized as "Less Utilized." Teachers report minimal use of SAS tools and strategies for lesson planning, accommodations, and modifications, which indicates a disconnect between readiness and practical application. Despite some engagement with SAS resources, such as referring to printed and web-based materials, many teachers do not consistently integrate these tools into their daily teaching practices. This underutilization could be attributed to the insufficient training and limited access to resources highlighted earlier. Moreover, the weak positive correlation found in Table 6 between readiness and effectiveness ($r = 0.499$) suggests that while readiness influences effectiveness, it is not the sole determining factor. Other elements, such as administrative support and access to adequate resources, may also play significant roles in improving SAS utilization and effectiveness (Sharma et al., 2019). Therefore, to maximize the impact of SAS, schools should not only focus on enhancing teacher readiness through professional development but also ensure teachers have the resources and support systems necessary for successful implementation.

Conclusion

The results of this study indicate that while teachers have a moderate level of readiness in terms of their basic knowledge, access to resources, and related training for implementing supplementary aids and services (SAS), there are significant gaps that hinder the full utilization of these supports. The overall readiness of teachers is categorized as "Somewhat Ready," and the extent of SAS utilization in classrooms is "Less

Utilized," suggesting that while teachers are aware of the importance of SAS, they are not consistently applying these tools in their teaching practices. Furthermore, the weak positive correlation between readiness and effectiveness suggests that improving teacher readiness alone may not be sufficient to fully optimize the use of SAS. Factors such as access to resources, comprehensive training, and administrative support are critical in ensuring the effectiveness of SAS in enhancing both the academic and social outcomes of students with disabilities. Therefore, targeted efforts to improve teacher training, resource allocation, and collaborative support systems are essential to maximize the potential benefits of SAS in inclusive education settings.

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